

Stories that matter Report

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[Stories that Matter](#) was the name of a series of art workshops that took place during the spring of 2024. It was an invitation to a group of asylum seekers to participate in a reflection on their experiences and how they have dealt with them.

In each session we discussed a topic related to migration and asylum seeking. Each topic was presented through an artistic activity, with the idea of encouraging the expression of those thoughts for which we often do not have words.

The activities were centered on objects that are part of a classic story about a journey. In this way, we had the opportunity to see migration from a different perspective each time.

To understand the logic of the workshops we have to imagine that we are about to embark on a journey. The first thing we have to do is to plan, with more or less haste, a destination, a route. To do this, we will have the help of **a map**. Then, we pack **our suitcase**. It can be a backpack, a bag.... In any case, it will be full of important objects for us. During the route, we need the documents that will allow us to cross borders until we reach our destination. In other words, we need **a passport** that identifies us. Finally, at our destination, we remember the people who stayed where we started our journey, to whom we write **a letter**.

MATERIALS

The implementation of the workshop required the fabrication of the objects that would be used by the participants.

Task 1. A world map, markers, stickers of various shapes and colors.

Task 2. A string, labels.

Task 3. Small books, stamps, colored pencils and markers, magazines, scissors and glue.

Task 4. Sheets of paper, postcards, fake stamps and envelopes.

Task 1. THE MAP

A map is a human invention that reflects boundaries according to geographic and political criteria. Undoubtedly, it is something that has a great impact on the world we live in.

However, how much of us is reflected in the most famous and canonical map? With this first activity we want to reflect on the experiences we have had through the delimitations of the world map.

How can we manipulate this map so that it reflects us? what can we add? what would we like to delete?

Task 2. THE SUITCASE

This time you will have to bring with you an object that was part of your suitcase and is still with you today. Now we are going to put this label where it says 'place' and 'person'. We have to write a place and a person with which we associate the object.

What does it mean to you? What does it represent?
Why did you choose it? Does it remind you of something that has happened to you?

We can also put a label on those objects that stayed there. What is the first one that comes to your mind? What does it mean to you?

Task 3. THE PASSPORT

When we open the passport, we find two axes that we will use to make a graph. The vertical axis represents a level of happiness or general satisfaction. The horizontal axis represents the passage of time.

On the time axis we will mark moments in our life that were important, indicating how old we were at the time. Then, we will give a score to each one according to the happiness axis. Each episode will be represented by a point that will be higher the happier we were at that time.

Finally, we mark with a dot of a different colour an event that has been particularly relevant to who we are.

What is reflected in these pages?
How could you explain what you have highlighted?

To fill in the next page of the passport we have to stop for a moment and think about that event in our life that has been pivotal. With this memory in mind, let's ask ourselves why we have chosen that moment, what changed, who we were before it happened, and after? To express this, we use the collage technique.

Finally, we stamp the passport. First, with a stamp that represents us. Then, we place stamps representing the people in our lives at a certain distance from where we have placed ourselves. **How close are they? How close do we feel them?**

Task 4. THE LETTER

In this activity the proposal is to write a letter to someone important in our lives. It can be something ordinary or imaginary, to someone close to us or someone further away...

As it is a fictitious letter, we can also think about those things we cannot say in real life.

Who have we chosen?

What things have we written?

What things would be impossible to communicate?

What prevents us from doing so?

To close the journey, we will imagine ourselves in the future. **Who will we be in a few years' time? Where will we be?**

Choose a postcard and write a short message to yourself. Maybe you choose to write an advice to yourself, to tell you what you hope to achieve by then, or perhaps a greeting will be enough....

5 KEY CONFLICTS IN THE SEARCH FOR ASYLUM

Methodology

In this study we used a qualitative approach to explore the needs of asylum seekers. The approach focuses on analyzing people's words, paying attention to their meaning and the value that participants attach to things.

This decision allows us to put the focus on the words of the participants and also on how all of us involved in the workshops relate to each other. In other words, it also allows us researchers to learn and transform ourselves personally along with them.

In addition, qualitative analysis helps us to highlight less tangible parts of our personality, such as artistic sensitivity and creativity. We consider this to be especially important in our study, as asylum seekers give us very clear examples of creating imaginative solutions to big problems.

Results of the analysis

As a result of this analysis we have identified 5 psychological needs that stand out in the asylum-seeking process. We have called these needs “conflicts”, to account for the fact that they are not only about covering a lack or filling holes.

Psychological conflicts are situations in which we find ourselves paralyzed by circumstances. They are complex problems in which reality seems contradictory and oppressive.

Science has taught us that the recipe for overcoming these obstacles includes two ingredients: learning from people who have been in similar circumstances and trying to think creatively. These are the two key ingredients in our workshop and with this study we ask ourselves, *does this also serve to better navigate the asylum-seeking process?*

01. HOME

*“It is my country of origin and
also the one that expelled me”*

The first conflict explored during the workshop deals with the concept we have of home.

This word usually refers to a place of comfort, a place to which we return to remember our past. For asylum seekers, however, it is a word with a conflicting meaning. It represents the place of familiarity and calm: a comfort zone. At the same time, for them, it is a place where one's life is in danger and must be abandoned.

For refugees, the word “home” is a place where danger and comfort coexist.

Participant: I'm going to put hearts
where I have family.

Facilitator: Spread out, that's how we
are all here.

Participant: All over the place...

The asylum-seeking process involves navigating this problem: noticing that you've had to leave your problem: noticing that you have had to leave the one you feel like home to live in another that you don't quite perceive as such.

For one participant, solving it is about giving a new and inclusive meaning to the word home.

"Part of the process implies that home is where you can have your affections, in a way, gather them together. The process of adaptation allows you to understand those things, obviously you can still miss, but I think... you can make home elsewhere. I do believe that. If you really want to... and well, conditions do influence, but I think that somehow we have to forget a little bit about the border issue. I hope that someday it will be over and we are all people, we are all human beings, instead of being Chilean, Argentinean, Peruvian... I mean, it is like categorizing, it is true, yes, yes... we belong, we come, we are born, but we belong to the world..."

02. PURPOSE

“Brother, you crossed an ocean, you are here and you don't know why you came?”

The second conflict explored during the workshop deals with the feeling of being lost after starting the migration process.

Once a person arrives in a new country, it becomes necessary to find a goal that gives meaning to the effort and the drastic change in life. The conflict seems to lie in the need to give meaning to migration and going beyond the crossing of an ocean or a land border.

"So, as long as you have a sense of who you are and where you are and what your purpose is, you will navigate life much better..."

As time goes by, the person learns to make sense of his or her experience. With this knowledge, one can become a true guide for those who have begun the process.

“You find yourself in a situation where you lost everything. Everything, everything, everything. So why do I bring it up? Because you become in a way a guide. If you are in an NGO that provides this type of help, obviously this contributes in some way to know how to speak, to expose a little of the experience you have had in the many years you have been away, with stressful situations, with extreme situations, with situations where you find yourself cursing the day you arrived “Why is this happening to me?” But as I say, the future is anxiety, the present is now. I mean, focus on the now, what is going to happen, neither you nor anyone else knows, but focus”.

03.

HOPE

“I have hope, but, at the same time, I don't...”

On many occasions, the efforts of people in search of asylum do not seem to yield the expected results. The challenges to be faced are neither few nor small and the path is not always clear, so it is common to feel desperate and disoriented.

"I said “I made a decision and it was not the right one, maybe at the time I thought about it, I believed, I saw a future...”. I analyzed it and all the things that one could achieve... all the things that one... got into my head and said “from being down I am going to be up, I am going to be able to help my family, I am going to take them out of there, for them to know, to feel the difference between living there and living here, the security... the environment... everything”. Well, right now we are at a point where we are not going up or down. I feel at a point where I don't know what is going to happen... I have hopes, but, at the same time, I don't have them".

This conflict, which can be experienced as frustration and discouragement, can be resolved by integrating the changes and valuing the lessons learned.

"We've all changed, as well as... a 180 degree turn in our lives. We have left, we have met, we have found that we can have a different life... And that, although the circumstances are not what we would like, in one way or another we feel better. In this migratory process that we have had, although there are difficulties that are hard, in one way or another they make us grow as a person. I mean, at the beginning you don't believe that you can achieve things, but as time goes by, as you fight against the current, you realize what you are really made of, that you have many capabilities, that you have hidden them, but in this type of circumstances is when they come out".

04.

BUREAU-

CRAZY

*“In the meantime I
had to be there...
in limbo...”*

Another major problem is the number of obstacles that the bureaucratic process itself imposes on attempts to normalize daily life. The asylum application is a necessary tool to achieve this goal, but at the same time it can be restrictive and can even be an impediment to achieving it.

It is an administrative process that is experienced with great uncertainty. In this situation, it becomes especially difficult to reorganize life in a new place.

“And if you get an unfavorable result, they give you 15 days to leave the center. And if you're studying, you're in college, or you're in something and you don't have anything else to do, you can't work or anything...”

Experiencing the solution to this conflict consists of understanding how the tool one needs can also be limiting. On many occasions, what we interpret as a weakness of ours is best explained by the circumstances we have to deal with.

“This is part of the bureaucracy, not having a work permit, not being able to have a good job, not being able to look for it, so that she can also work, so that both can earn on the same side, so that they can make an enterprise or something. Why? Because the same situation ties you down and forces you to stand still for a certain period of time... and that is why many homes, many families are broken and there comes a time when everyone does not have the same strength. Where weakness falls and you are not strong, it knocks you down”.

05.

MOURNING

“When my dad died... there was no time to cry”

The death of a family member who was in the home country may mark the beginning of an internal conflict for the asylum seeker. This may cause the person to realize what he or she is missing in his or her home country.

Being unable to return to say goodbye to the deceased, the person experiences grief in a doubly complicated way. This event highlights the perceived distance from the country of origin and the fact that life continues to go on there, even though one is not present. The reality of the death is more difficult to assimilate from a distance, although rationally one is able to understand it.

“I am convinced that I have not said goodbye to my old man because I will say goodbye to him the day I enter his house and I feel that he is no longer there. For me, that day is the day my father dies, because I have not yet, that is, I was not there. I knew because I did, that is, phone, mom, this, that... but there was no time to cry because we had to work, otherwise we were not going to pay rent, we were not going to pay for food”.

One way to elaborate this conflict is to experience the memory of the deceased person from the present. That is to say, beyond the fact that the farewell takes place physically, the image of the deceased person occupies a concrete, permanent and significant place in the person's world..

“Yes, there is that pending farewell. Because I know that that moment will be the one in which I will assume that my father is really gone. Because he left without me being with him. So for me he is still there. He is still far away... He is still on a trip and still not.... I haven't assumed that he's gone. I know he's not, of course, and... it's that yes, the dead is really dead when he's forgotten. The way to keep him alive is to keep him in your heart, he will always be there, in your memory. In what you can model what he was, what he did and what he taught you. There he is alive, there he is present.”

EXPERIENCING CONFLICTS

The search for asylum involves experiencing conflicts on a psychological level. Unlike a dilemma, these are not resolved by simply opting for one of the options presented, but by creating a creative and different solution.

It is my place of comfort and it is also a dangerous place.

I have hope for the future, but at the same time I do not.

Life goes on and the land from which I departed from is no longer the same.

It is clear to me why I have migrated and at the same time I am lost.

I need the bureaucracy to get asylum, but the bureaucracy infantilizes me and keeps me in uncertainty.

During the workshops, these issues played a greater or lesser role depending on the moment of the migration process discussed in the conversation.

According to the testimonies, it seems that some conflicts have been harder to experience than others. Those that are activated when talking about the first decision to migrate are the most sensitive.

"When I had to narrate when I left my country. The most difficult decision I could have made was that and yes, remembering that moment... it is an accumulation of sensations that remain the bad ones."

Presence of different psychological conflicts in the life stories of the participants.:

Talking about conflicts seems to be one of the best ways to deal with them, as this allows us to experience them instead of avoiding them. However, this experience can be painful, so it is advisable to choose an appropriate time to do so.

Participant 1: The day I felt most uncomfortable was when we were asked to bring something, a memory, that was the most difficult one because it is to relive it, all the pain and all that feeling that comes with bringing more memories and all the people we have left behind... That has been the most difficult.

Facilitator: Sometimes memories you bring them back and keep them until you feel able to see them, right?

Participant 1: Yes, exactly.

Facilitator: You avoid them... and you don't face them... and you don't face them.

Participant 2: But it is healing! You have to face them and do it. Because it was hard for me too, when I brought them... and those things like that I kept them in a little box to make you realize that you don't have them, that they are there, but they are not there, but... to give them the courage and say “It is part of me, it is part of me, it is here and I have to get it out”, that is why it is healing. And that is one of the things that the workshop achieved.

Has anything changed about you after the workshop?

“Yes, it has changed somewhat. It's changed that I'm more...I kind of self-evaluate. I kind of say out loud what I'm doing. First is that I'm thinking more, before I was more impulsive and I think I'm taking more time. After the timing thing, after the chart, I'm taking more time, like I say, it was healing, in my case. It has been healing. I'm taking more time, I'm not taking things personally.”

“I was carrying a lot of emotional baggage inside and...it was a way to release that baggage that I was carrying around from many years ago and get my feet on the ground and think about the future, what do I want, what do I expect to happen and how am I going to get it.”

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“Yes. Because I used to worry a lot about what other people think of my life. A lot. But now I don't worry about that. I'm going to do what I need to go forward and what's good for me and what I like.
Yes. Before I had doubts, now I think what I'm doing is the right thing.”

“I have lived the migratory process quite calmly. With a lot of resilience, with a lot of... You know? Reinventing myself every day, but aware of where I am, what are the procedures, the laws, what is within my reach and what is not. Because there are things that normally you can't control. And yes, I add myself... because I am convinced that knowledge does not take up space and it is always an enriching experience to have in the present. In other words, it does add up. I haven't started to analyze if anything has changed, but it does add up, of course it does.”

The creative reflection that took place during the workshops served to bring to light the internal conflicts of the participants.

As it is suggested in the context of psychotherapy, this could be the first step towards a solution, since experiencing conflicts can help us to define our own way of dealing with them.

In conclusion:

Seeking asylum is a process that goes beyond making a physical movement between countries. The testimonies presented in this report show that it is also a psychological process marked by conflicts and contradictions that can often be painful to experience.

Five specific psychological conflicts were identified: the notion of home as a place of comfort and danger, the presence and absence of hope for the future, creating a purpose of migrating once the border crossing has been achieved, the need to adjust one's life to a particularly suffocating bureaucratic process, and the impact of grief over the the death of family members in the country of origin.

The workshops showed that in order to find solutions to the critical conflicts involved in the search for asylum, it is particularly useful to enhance creativity. Also, to talk with and learn about the experience of other people involved in the same process can be key to finding healing solutions.

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